

Low-noise supercontinuum using a 1.85 μm fs pump in elliptical-core and normal-dispersion ZBLAN fibres

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Abstract

We have developed a novel, low-noise 1.85 μm femtosecond (fs) pump delivering 58 fs pulses at 210 mW, with a 40 MHz repetition rate and a low relative intensity noise (RIN) of 0.41%. We identified two elliptical-core, polarisation-maintaining ZBLAN fibres with core dimensions of 6.7 \times 2.7 μm and 8.9 \times 4.1 μm that exhibit all-normal-dispersion in the region of interest. By pumping these fibres with the 1.85 μm source, we generated an ultra-low-noise supercontinuum (SC) in the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre, spanning 1.500–2.251 μm at the -40 dB level, with a minimum RIN of 0.22% at 1.7 μm . The SC from the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre spans 1.465–2.297 μm at the -40 dB level, with a minimum RIN of 0.36% at 2.0 μm . To achieve higher peak power, the 58 fs pulses were soliton-compressed to sub-10 fs durations. The resulting pulse was coupled into the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm fibre, producing an ultra-low-noise SC spanning 0.771–2.724 μm , with a measured RIN as low as 0.21% at 2.1 μm .

Keywords: All-normal-dispersion ZBLAN fibres, polarisation-maintaining, ultra-low-noise supercontinuum, relative-intensity noise, thulium amplifier, ultrafast laser

1. Introduction

Ultra-low-noise supercontinuum (SC) generation (SCG) can be realised using femtosecond (fs) pump pulses in polarisation-maintaining (PM) all-normal-dispersion (ANDi) fibres. In the femtosecond pulse duration regime, spectral broadening arises from self-phase modulation (SPM) and optical wave-breaking (OWB) [1]. As these processes are deterministic, the resulting SC can exhibit negligible pulse-to-pulse fluctuation [2]. Spectra with flatness better than ± 1 dB have been achieved [3]. In addition, the temporal waveform can remain a single, well-defined pulse without break-up.

When a femtosecond pump is used with a low-birefringence fibre of given normal-dispersion, achieving ultra-low-noise SC depends critically on the pulse duration, peak power, and fibre length [4]. In low-birefringence ANDi fibres, coupling between the two orthogonally polarised fundamental modes can drive polarisation-mode instability (PMI) [5], which degrades the SC noise characteristics [6, 7]. Using a PM ANDi fibre and launching on the fast axis suppresses PMI and related vector instabilities, thereby preserving extremely low pulse-to-pulse fluctuations [8].

Ultra-low-noise SC has been extensively studied in a variety of silica-based fibres. Although ANDi-fibre-based SC does not span the full transmission window of silica—from wavelengths shorter than 0.40 μm to longer than 2.40 μm —by selecting appropriate pump sources and suitable speciality fibres, distinct bands in the visible and near-infrared (NIR) can be generated. For example, a microstructured ANDi fibre with a minimum-dispersion wavelength (MDW) near 0.65 μm generated an SC spanning 0.42–0.90 μm at the -20 dB spectral level when pumped with 50 fs pulses at 0.65 μm [9]. In a germanium-doped silica ANDi fibre with MDW at 1.56 μm , pumping with 110 fs pulses at 1.68 μm generated a flat SC spanning 1.30–2.00 μm at the -20 dB level [3].

Ultra-low-noise SC enables a range of NIR applications that were previously out of reach because the high pulse-to-pulse fluctuations of traditional SC sources—despite their very broad bandwidth—limited sensitivity and stability. For example, in ultra-high-resolution scanning near-field optical microscopy (SNOM) [10], the low relative-intensity noise (RIN) allows detection of weak signals extracted from higher-order demodulated components. In shot-noise-limited dual-comb SC [11],

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two ultra-low-noise SC spectra are generated in a single ANDi fibre; each inherits the intrinsically low RIN of femtosecond-pumped ANDi SC, and the resulting source supports shot-noise-limited detection. In optical coherence tomography (OCT), traditional SC sources have been used to achieve better axial resolution than swept-source systems; however, unlike swept-source-based OCT, they have not enabled shot-noise-limited detection because of high pulse-to-pulse fluctuations. By contrast, ultra-low-noise SC can deliver shot-noise-limited, ultra-high-resolution OCT [12], providing higher contrast, reduced background, and extended imaging depth compared with systems based on traditional SC.

Extending low-noise SC into the mid-infrared (MIR) requires suitable fibres and appropriate femtosecond pump sources. Fluoride-glass fibres offer broad transparency—from wavelengths shorter than 0.30 to longer than 5.0 μm —and are therefore attractive hosts for MIR SC. To date, most MIR SC in fluoride fibres has been pumped in the anomalous-dispersion regime, yielding spectra, for example, from 0.8 μm to longer than 4.5 μm [13]. However, achieving ultra-low-noise operation requires that the broadening occurs entirely within the normal-dispersion region [14]. Until recently, this was impeded by the lack of suitable normal-dispersion fluoride fibres. In this work, we investigate SC generation in normal-dispersion, PM ZBLAN fibres and demonstrate a pathway to generate ultra-low-noise SC in these fibres.

2. Thulium-doped fibre-based 1.85 μm amplifier

To obtain a low-noise femtosecond source beyond 1.56 μm , an ultra-low-noise SC is first generated in an ANDi silica fibre using a 1.56 μm Erbium (Er):fibre femtosecond laser. The 1.85 μm portion of this spectrum is then amplified, rather than seeding directly at 2 μm [15, 16]. This avoids anomalous-dispersion regime, fibre-based nonlinear stages that can introduce pulse-to-pulse fluctuations [17]. By decoupling seed generation and stretching from amplification and compression, this approach provides the flexibility to enable a low-noise 1.85 μm source.

2.1 Chirped-pulse amplification at 1.85 μm

A 1.56 μm Er:fibre laser delivers 110 fs full width at half maximum (FWHM) pulses at a 40 MHz repetition rate. An optical isolator prevents back-reflections into the laser cavity; two low group-delay-dispersion mirrors are used for beam steering; and a half-wave plate aligns the polarisation to one of the principal axes of the fibre. Light is coupled into PM1550 fibre using an aspheric-lens-based collimator. The pulse undergoes soliton compression; after 6.2 cm of PM1550, the FWHM duration is reduced to ~ 16 fs. The PM1550 section is spliced to 55 cm of PM2000D ANDi fibre, forming a hybrid fibre system as described in Ref. [18]. The resulting SC spans wavelengths from shorter than 1 μm to beyond 2 μm while preserving a single-pulse temporal structure. The pulse is then dispersively stretched to longer than 9 ps in 67 cm of PM2000D to avoid nonlinear reshaping prior to amplification.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of the thulium-doped fibre based chirped pulse amplifier operating at 1.85 μm . (b) Spectra at the points indicated in (a): S1, after WDM 2 in blue, and S2, after final compression in green.

The measured group-velocity dispersion (GVD) of PM1550 and PM2000D is reported in Ref. [18], and the measurement technique and the GVD values of PM2000D are given in Ref. [19]. PM1550 has its zero-dispersion wavelength at 1.34 μm and exhibits anomalous dispersion at longer wavelengths. PM2000D is ANDi across its transmission window, with the

longer-wavelength transmission edge around 2.4 μm . These dispersion properties are responsible for the soliton compression in PM1550 at 1.56 μm and the low-noise broadening and dispersive stretching in PM2000D.

The schematic of the thulium-doped fibre chirped-pulse amplifier (CPA) operating at 1.85 μm is shown in Figure 1(a). Amplification of the 1.85 μm band is performed in 14.5 cm of PM thulium-doped fibre using wavelength-division multiplexer (WDM) 1, which combines a 1.56 μm continuous-wave (CW) pump with the stretched seed; WDM 2 removes residual 1.56 μm CW light. The spectrum after WDM 2, labelled S1 in Figure 1(a), is plotted in Figure 1(b) in blue. Final compression in 36.7 cm of PM1550 compensates accumulated dispersion and yields 58 fs pulses. The pulse duration was measured by performing intensity autocorrelation and assuming a Gaussian temporal profile. The corresponding output spectrum, labelled S2 in Figure 1(a), is shown in Figure 1(b) in green. The average power in the 1.85 μm region is ~ 10 mW before amplification and 210 mW after amplification and final compression, corresponding to a fully PM, coherently seeded thulium CPA delivering 58 fs pulses at 1.85 μm at 40 MHz.

3. Normal-dispersion and PM ZBLAN fibre-based SCG

To extend ultra-low-noise SC towards the MIR, two elliptical-core, PM ZBLAN fibres with normal dispersion were identified. The linearly polarised output of the 1.85 μm femtosecond source was aligned to one of the principal axes of each fibre, and the resulting SC at the fibre output was recorded on an optical spectrum analyser (OSA).

3.1 Measured GVD and group birefringence

Broadband measurements of GVD and group birefringence were performed to characterise the two fibres with core dimensions 6.7 \times 2.7 μm and 8.9 \times 4.1 μm . The GVD of the fibres was measured by white-light spectral interferometry for the two orthogonal fundamental modes of each fibre as described in Ref. [20]. The measurement range spans 1.4–4.3 μm . For the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre, the measured GVD remains normal to 3.77 μm and is plotted in Figure 2(a) for one of the orthogonal fundamental modes. For the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre, the measured GVD remains normal to 3.25 μm and is plotted in Figure 2(b).

The group birefringence was measured by crossed [21–23] and aligned-polariser methods. These are complementary methods, and the group birefringence values were averaged to obtain the mean group birefringence. For the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre, measurements were obtained over 1.87–3.95 μm . The fibre exhibits relatively strong birefringence varying between 2×10^{-4} and 4×10^{-4} across this range. The measured group birefringence for the fibre is shown in Figure 2(c). For the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre, measurements were obtained over 1.96–3.59 μm . The birefringence is on the order of 1×10^{-4} . The measured group birefringence for the fibre is shown in Figure 2(d). With measured normal dispersion and relatively strong birefringence, these fibres are suitable for generating ultra-low-noise SC when pumped by a femtosecond source, where the SC can extend to 3.77 μm and 3.25 μm , respectively.

Figure 2. Experimentally measured GVDs: 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre (a) with normal dispersion up to 3.77 μm , and 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre (b) with normal dispersion up to 3.25 μm . Experimentally measured group birefringence of the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre (c) and the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre (d).

3.2 SCG in normal-dispersion, elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibres

The PM1550 output of the 1.85 μm femtosecond laser was prepared as a cleaved bare-fibre facet. The ZBLAN input and output end facets were cleaved using a Vytran cleaver. Light was coupled from the PM1550 fibre into the ZBLAN fibre by physical contact. The PM1550 output fibre was mounted on a rotation stage, and the launch polarisation was rotated to align with a principal axis of the ZBLAN fibre. The rotation mount was placed on a three-axis translation stage; the ZBLAN fibre was also mounted on a three-axis translation stage for fine adjustment during coupling. The coupling scheme is shown in Figure 4, in section 4. The coupling efficiency was calculated as the ratio of the average power measured after the ZBLAN fibre and a collimating lens to the average power at the 1.85 μm amplifier output. The spectra at the ZBLAN output were measured using an OSA (Yokogawa) covering 1.2–2.4 μm .

The coupling efficiency into the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre was 61%. The fibre length was 1.55 m. The SC from this fibre spans 1.500–2.251 μm at -40 dB, corresponding to a spectral bandwidth of 0.751 μm . The spectrum is plotted in Figure 3(a). The coupling efficiency into the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre was 78%. The fibre length was 2 m. The SC from this fibre spans 1.465–2.297 μm at -40 dB, corresponding to a spectral bandwidth of 0.832 μm . The spectrum is plotted in Figure 3(b). In both fibres, the entire generated SC lies within the measured normal-dispersion region. In fact, the long-wavelength edge of the SC is far from the edge of the normal-dispersion region in each fibre.

Figure 3. SC spectra from the normal-dispersion, elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibres. (a) 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre: SC spans 1.500–2.251 μm at -40 dB. (b) 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre: SC spans 1.465–2.297 μm at -40 dB. Corresponding band-pass-filtered spectra are plotted for the SC from both fibres. The peaks of the filtered spectra are vertically offset by -45 dB for clarity.

To evaluate the noise properties of the SC, spectrally resolved pulse-to-pulse RIN measurements were performed using an electronic spectrum analyser (ESA) [24] on band-pass-filtered SC. The corresponding band-pass-filtered spectra are plotted together with the SC in the figure. The filtered spectra have a FWHM of ~ 20 nm. The peaks of the band-pass-filtered spectra are vertically offset by -45 dB for clarity.

4. ESA-based RIN measurement

To measure the pulse-to-pulse energy fluctuations in terms of RIN, light was focused onto the photodetector using a lens. The electrical signal from the photodetector was low-pass filtered to half the repetition rate of the laser using an electronic low-pass filter. The filtered signal was then coupled into the ESA through a direct current (DC) block to prevent any DC voltage from reaching the analyser input, as the ESA does not accept any DC voltage. All RIN measurements in this work were performed over 100 Hz–20 MHz. Since the pulse train samples the intensity at f_{rep} , the amplitude-noise spectrum is only uniquely defined up to the Nyquist frequency $f_{rep}/2=20$ MHz; so, 20 MHz is the maximum noise frequency in this setup.

To measure the RIN of the light from the 1.85 μm pump, the output of the PM1550 fibre was first collimated and then focused onto the photodetector. The RIN of the 1.85 μm pump was measured to be 0.41%.

4.1 Spectrally resolved RIN of the SC

A single, broadband RIN measurement of the SC can be misleading, because noise variations at different wavelengths may partially cancel and yield an artificially low overall RIN. To accurately assess the underlying noise, it is important to perform narrowband spectral filtering of the SC. This approach can reveal wavelength-dependent noise characteristics and can provide insight into, for example, whether SCG occurs in a coherent or an incoherent regime. Therefore, for the ESA-based RIN measurement of the SC, a linear-variable filter (LVF) is used to perform narrowband spectral filtering. In

addition, the ESA-based measurement provides the noise PSD as a function of the electronic frequency. From this, various noise sources can be identified: higher-frequency noise, from a few kHz into the MHz range, up to $f_{rep}/2$, can originate from gain and intracavity pulse-formation dynamics, and from modulation instability, which can generate broadband excess noise extending into the MHz range. By contrast, low electronic frequency noise is typically dominated by pump-power drift and mechanical vibration, among others.

The full schematic of the spectrally resolved, ESA-based RIN measurement set-up for the SC out of the elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibre is shown in Figure 4. The schematic shows the light from the 1.85 μm thulium-doped CPA, delivered by a PM1550 fibre with a cleaved bare-fibre facet, is coupled by physical contact into the ZBLAN fibre. The SC from the ZBLAN is first collimated using lens 1. To perform narrowband filtering, the collimated light is focused onto the LVF using lens 2. After passing through the LVF, the light is re-collimated by lens 3 and then focused onto the photodetector using lens 4 to ensure that the light falls into the centre of the detector's active area. The electrical signal from the photodetector is processed as described above.

Figure 4. Schematic of the spectrally resolved, ESA-based pulse-to-pulse RIN measurement set-up showing the 1.85 μm thulium-doped CPA and the elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibre.

The ESA measures the electrical noise PSD from the photodetector in V^2/Hz . This is converted to RIN by normalising the PSD to the square of the measured DC level V_{DC} , measured before the DC block, and the result is expressed as dBc/Hz. Here, dBc means decibels relative to the carrier, where the carrier is defined as the mean DC signal level corresponding to the detected optical power. The spectrum is therefore expressed relative to that average level per unit bandwidth. The RIN is obtained by integrating the normalised noise PSD from 100 Hz up to $f_{rep}/2=20$ MHz, taking the square root, and expressing the result as a percentage.

Spectrally resolved RIN measurements were performed for the SC from both fibres. For the 6.7×2.7 μm core fibre, the RIN was measured from 1.50–2.15 μm in steps of ~ 50 nm. For the 8.9×4.1 μm core fibre, the RIN was measured from 1.50–2.20 μm in steps of ~ 50 nm. Outside these ranges, the detected power was insufficient to perform the RIN measurement. The spectral slices had a FWHM of ~ 20 nm, determined by the LVF passband and the beam spot size on the LVF. Figure 5(a) shows the spectrally resolved RIN of the SC from the 6.7×2.7 μm fibre in green and from the 8.9×4.1 μm fibre in blue.

The 6.7×2.7 μm core fibre exhibits a minimum RIN of 0.22% at 1.70 μm , and the 8.9×4.1 μm core fibre exhibits a minimum RIN of 0.36% at 2.00 μm . For both fibres, the RIN is lowest near the centre of the SC spectrum and increases towards the spectral edges. The 6.7×2.7 μm core fibre shows a stronger increase in RIN towards the edges than the 8.9×4.1 μm core fibre, consistent with the narrower SC bandwidth achieved in the experiments with the smaller-core fibre. In both fibres, a pronounced RIN peak is observed near the centre of the SC and coincides with a dip in the SC spectrum. This elevated RIN is attributed to the reduced optical power in the dip region and to sensitivity to non-ideal spectral and temporal structure of the femtosecond pump and the resulting SC as discussed in Ref. [25]. Away from the dip regions, the RIN remains low, confirming that both fibres support ultra-low-noise SCG.

As shown in Figure 5(a), the RIN near the centre of the SC is lower than the RIN of the femtosecond pump for the SC generated in both fibres. This behaviour has also been reported previously; in that work, the RIN was measured using an oscilloscope [14]. The noise PSD for the two measurements at 1.7 μm and 1.9 μm is shown in Figure 5(b), plotted versus electronic frequency for the SC from the 6.7×2.7 μm core fibre. Also shown is the noise floor, measured with the optical input blocked, obtained using the same photodetector and ESA settings as in the optical measurement. The 1.9 μm point corresponds to a local maximum in the spectrally resolved RIN, whereas 1.7 μm corresponds to the RIN minimum for this SC. Compared with 1.7 μm , the noise PSD at 1.9 μm is elevated by approximately 18 dB at electronic frequencies above a few kHz and is approximately frequency-independent in this region, consistent with an increased white-noise contribution.

The noise PSD corresponding to the spectrally resolved RIN at 1.7 μm alone, plotted versus electronic frequency for the SC from the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre, is shown in Figure 5(c). The corresponding cumulative contribution to the RIN obtained by integrating the noise PSD over electronic frequency is shown in Figure 5(d). The integration plot indicates that the dominant contribution to the RIN arises from the several-kHz to few-MHz range. This behaviour is consistent with residual pump noise transferred to the SC, where gain dynamics and intracavity pulse-formation processes can contribute in this frequency range. The observed roll-off of the noise PSD towards higher frequencies indicates that these noise

Figure 5. RIN and noise PSD plots for SC from the elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibres. (a) Spectrally resolved RIN versus wavelength for the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre in green and the 8.9 \times 4.1 μm core fibre in blue. (b) Noise PSD versus electronic frequency at 1.7 and 1.9 μm for the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre, and the noise floor for the measurements. (c) Noise PSD versus electronic frequency at 1.7 μm for the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core fibre. (d) Cumulative contribution to the RIN obtained by integrating the noise PSD over electronic frequency.

mechanisms have a limited effective bandwidth, so that above approximately 10 MHz the amplitude noise becomes small and, as the frequency approaches 20 MHz, the measured noise PSD tends towards the detector and ESA noise floor. At low electronic frequencies below the kHz range, the contribution to the integrated RIN is small; any remaining increase at the lowest frequencies is more likely to originate from non-intrinsic effects such as slow environmental perturbations, including mechanical vibration, rather than from the pump or the SCG process itself.

5. SCG with sub-10 fs input pulse

In normal-dispersion fibres pumped with femtosecond pulses, the bandwidth of spectral broadening increases with peak power [26]. To increase the peak power launched into the ZBLAN fibre in our case, the 58 fs pulses from the 1.85 μm thulium-doped fibre amplifier were soliton-compressed to sub-10 fs in PMHN5 fibre. The PMHN5 fibre was spliced directly to the PM1550 output of the 1.85 μm amplifier.

The spectral and temporal evolution in PMHN5 was modelled using the generalised nonlinear Schrödinger equation (GNLSE) in the interaction picture [27, 28]. The simulations predict a maximum temporal compression at a PMHN5 length of 1.2 cm, where the temporal FWHM is sub-10 fs. A similar compression scheme was used in Ref. [29]. To experimentally map the spectral evolution in PMHN5, a cut-back measurement was performed starting from a 3 cm fibre length. The fibre was shortened in 2 mm steps, and the output spectrum was recorded after each cut. The spectra were measured using two Yokogawa OSAs covering the wavelength ranges 0.6–1.7 μm and 1.2–2.4 μm .

The simulated and measured spectral evolution along the PMHN5 fibre is shown in Figure 6(a) and (b), respectively. The dashed line in Figure 6(a) marks the simulated compression point at 1.2 cm. In the experiment, the spectra show the closest agreement in spectral shape with the simulated spectrum at the compression point when the PMHN5 fibre length is 1.6 cm; this experimentally determined length is marked by the dashed line in Figure 6(b). The average power measured after the PMHN5 fibre was 206 mW. The pulse-to-pulse RIN of the sub-10 fs pulse was measured to be 0.52%.

The sub-10 fs pulse was coupled into the fundamental mode of the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm core ZBLAN fibre using the same physical-contact coupling arrangement described above. The ZBLAN fibre length was 1.55 m and the coupling efficiency

Figure 6. Simulated (a) and measured (b) spectral evolution along the length of PMHN5 fibre during soliton compression of the 1.85 μm pulses. (c) Measured SC at the output of the 6.7 \times 2.7 μm elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibre pumped with the sub-10 fs pulse, together with the filtered spectra used for the RIN measurements. The filtered spectra are vertically offset by -45 dB for clarity. The corresponding spectrally resolved RIN is plotted with respect to the right-hand y-axis.

was 58%. The experimental SC at the fibre output was obtained by stitching measurements from instruments covering different wavelength ranges: an OSA spanning 0.60–1.70 μm (Yokogawa), an OSA spanning 1.20–2.40 μm (Yokogawa), and a WaveScan spectrometer spanning 1.5–6.3 μm (APE). The resulting SC spans 0.771–2.724 μm at the -40 dB level. As in the case of the SC generated in the normal-dispersion, elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibres pumped by 58 fs pulses, the pulse-to-pulse RIN remains extremely low across the spectrum, with elevated RIN only in spectral regions containing pronounced dips. The RIN is as low as 0.21% at 2.1 μm . The measured SC is plotted in Figure 6(c) together with the band-pass-filtered spectra used for the RIN measurements. The filtered spectra are vertically offset by -45 dB for clarity. The corresponding spectrally resolved pulse-to-pulse RIN is also plotted in Figure 6(c) with respect to the right-hand y-axis.

6. Conclusion

A low-noise 1.85 μm femtosecond pump was developed using a fully PM, coherently seeded thulium-doped CPA with decoupled seed generation and stretching from amplification and compression. The source delivers 58 fs pulses at 210 mW average power and 40 MHz repetition rate with a measured RIN of 0.41%, providing a robust platform for low-noise pumping beyond 1.56 μm . Two elliptical-core PM ZBLAN fibres with core dimensions 6.7 \times 2.7 μm and 8.9 \times 4.1 μm were characterised by broadband measurements of GVD and group birefringence and were found to exhibit normal dispersion across the relevant wavelength range.

Pumping these fibres with the 1.85 μm , 58 fs source produced ultra-low-noise SC spanning 1.500–2.251 μm and 1.465–2.297 μm at the -40 dB level, with minimum RIN values of 0.22% and 0.36%, respectively. Soliton compression in PMHN5 to sub-10 fs increased the launched peak power and enabled broader ultra-low-noise SC spanning 0.771–2.724 μm at the -40 dB level with RIN as low as 0.21% at 2.1 μm , thereby extending ultra-low-noise SC into the short-wavelength MIR.

These results establish a pathway towards further extension of ultra-low-noise SC deeper into the MIR. In particular, longer-wavelength pumps around 2.8 μm or beyond used with the PM ZBLAN fibres characterised in this work, or in conjunction with tailored normal-dispersion fluoride fibre designs optimised for those pump bands, provide a route to broader MIR coverage while preserving the low-noise characteristics associated with ANDi fibre based and femtosecond pumped SC.

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